

The contribution of mechanisms of moral disengagement to dating violence and aggression in adolescents

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Abstract

Objectives: In this study, the relationships between the mechanisms of moral disengagement and aggression and dating violence in adolescents and young adults were analysed. **Method:** Measures of moral disengagement and different forms of aggression (physical and verbal) and dating violence (physical and verbal-emotional), were obtained from a sample of 424 people (61.1% women) aged 15 to 25 years. **Results:** Significant correlations between the different mechanisms of moral disengagement (*depersonalization*, *irresponsibility*, and *rationalization*) and aggression, especially physical aggression, and correlations of lower magnitude with dating violence. Once the variables sex, age and social desirability were controlled, the mechanisms of moral disengagement predicted 11% of the variance in physical aggression, 5% of the variance in verbal aggression and 2% of variance in verbal-emotional abuse in dating. *Depersonalization* and *rationalization* were the best predictors for physical aggression, *rationalization* best predicted verbal aggression, while *irresponsibility* was exclusively a predictor for verbal-emotional violence in dating relationships. **Conclusions:** Moral disengagement seems to play a more important role in aggression in general (physical and verbal) than in dating violence. It would be desirable for children and adolescents to know the concept of moral disengagement and its influence on aggression and to include the mechanisms of moral disengagement in programmes for the prevention of violence in adolescents and young adults.

Keywords: aggression; adolescents; dating violence; moral disengagement

The *Social Cognitive Theory* (Bandura, 1983, 1986) proposes that individuals possess certain self-regulatory mechanisms that contribute to maintaining their behaviour in line with their internal rules, inhibiting behaviours that are considered culturally to be harmful or inhuman (Bandura, 1990; Bandura, Barbaranelli, Caprara, & Pastorelli, 1996). The disengagement of such self-regulatory mechanisms, and of the moral self-sanctions mediated by different psychological and social processes, would favour the breaching of social norms and the disinhibition of aggressive, immoral and inhuman behaviours (Bandura, 1990, 2002; White, Bandura, & Vero, 2009). From other theoretical approaches, different psychological mechanisms very similar to deactivation of self-censure and moral self-regulation have been proposed (see Ribeaud & Eisner, 2010, for a review). On the one hand, within *Theory of Delinquency*, Sykes and Matza (1957) proposed several techniques of sociological neutralization related to *denial of responsibility and injury*, *denial of victim*, *claim rightful retaliation*, *blame to others*, and the *appeal to loyalty* to transgressive peers (Osofsky, Bandura, & Zimbardo, 2005). On the other hand, Barriga and Gibbs (1996) refer to the *Secondary Self-Serving Cognitive Distortions* consisting of rationalizations that serve to neutralize conscience or guilt, such as, *blaming others*, *minimizing/mislabelling the harm or consequences*, or *assuming the worst*. Therefore, under different labels would be including psychological mechanisms of restructuration cognitive, minimizing own agency, disregarding/distorting negative impact, blaming/dehumanizing the victim, condemnation of condemner and assuming the worst (Ribeaud & Eisner, 2010). All these psychological and socio-moral mechanisms involving selective deactivation of self-regulatory processes and moral censure have been developed and included under the construct of *moral disengagement* (hereinafter MD) by Bandura and colleagues (Bandura, 1990, 2002; Bandura et al., 1996) to try to explain why some people inflict suffering on others (Azzi, 2011; Bandura, 1986, 2002; Obermann, 2011a).

Moral disengagement mechanisms

Several MD mechanisms have been described by Bandura et al. (1996): (1) *Moral justification*: Immoral acts or detrimental conduct are made acceptable by portraying them in the service of higher moral purposes; (2) *Euphemistic labelling*: Injurious conduct or immoral activities are made benign through sanitized and convoluted verbiage; (3) *Advantageous comparison*: One's injurious conduct can seem benevolent or less harmful compared to other people's conduct; (4) *Displacement of responsibility*: Responsibility for one's harmful conduct or transgressions can be ascribed to others or the circumstances because of situational pressures or other people's demands; (5) *Diffusion of responsibility*: Individuals are able to diffuse or disclaim personal responsibility when a group are engaging in the same injurious behaviour; (6) *Distortion of consequences*: People can legitimate one's transgressions or immoral acts by minimizing or disregarding the harmful consequences of one's actions; (7) *Dehumanization*: Self-censure reactions can be disengaged or blunted by viewing victims as subhuman creatures unable to experience normal or real feelings and not deserving to be treated as human beings; and 8) *Attribution of blame*: Victims get blamed for bringing suffering on themselves and for provoking one to behave immorally or violent toward them.

Moral disengagement and violence

The disinhibitory and legitimizing effects of MD on physical violence were shown in studies from the 1970's (Bandura, Underwood, & Fromson, 1975; Haney, Banks, & Zimbardo, 1973). More recently, studies carried out on community-based samples of adolescents and young adults have shown a significant positive correlation between MD and aggression, as well as the ability to predict physical, psychological and relational violence (Bandura et al., 1996; Carmárk & Blatný, 1995; Hyde, Shaw, & Moilanen, 2010; Hymel, Rocke-Henderson, & Bonanno, 2005; Obermann, 2011a, 2011b; Paciello, Fida, Tramontano, Lupinetti, & Caprara, 2008; Pornari & Wood, 2010). However, MD remains virtually unexplored in the particular case of dating

violence (DV), with only a couple of studies focusing on the relationship between certain aspects of moral reasoning and DV (Feiring, Deblinger, Hoch-Espada, & Haworth, 2002; Author citation, in press). In the first of these (Feiring et al., 2002), externalizing responsibility for harm to others was related to men using physical aggression in dating relationships, and low levels of guilt and shame were related to the justification of sexual aggression. Furthermore, a significant relationship was detected between MD and violence committed by males aged between 16 and 18 (Author citation, in press). Moreover, the relationship between moral justification and inflicted violence was moderated by the dehumanization of the victim. Nevertheless, despite the studies carried out to date, the specific mechanisms of MD that are related to the different manifestations of aggressive and violent behaviour remain to be determined. The more primary and maladaptive nature of the physical aggression during advanced stages of development (Brame, Nagin & Tremblay, 2001; Loeber & Hay, 1997), and the more intense contribution of MD to physical aggression as opposed to verbal aggression.

It is also likely that the nature of the physical aggression, usually more serious than verbal aggression, facilitates its association with mechanisms of moral depersonalization. This process involves a dehumanized perception of the victim (*dehumanization*) and attributing blame (*attribution of blame*), rather than other more independent moral mechanisms of the victim that operate in domains distinct to the locus of the recipient of the action (i.e.: the behavioural locus, action locus and outcome locus), for example responsibility (*advantageous comparison, displacement of responsibility and diffusion of responsibility*) or rationalization (*moral justification, euphemistic labelling and distortion of consequences*; Bandura, 1990, 2002). In any case, these concepts are more speculative than empirical and thus, further studies are needed to clarify the connections mentioned above. To date, no studies have analysed whether association of MD with the different aggressive manifestations would provide a better understanding of the role that these moral mechanisms play in the different types of aggression

and violence. Indeed, defining these relationships would help establish the nomological network of aggression and MD, and improve the scope of these constructs. Aggression in general, and DV in particular, are currently considered as a serious social and public health problem (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2012; Kaura & Lohman, 2008; Teten, Ball, Valley, Noonan & Rosenbluth, 2009). Hence, better knowledge of the variables associated with these phenomena would help to predict and control such outbreaks.

The present study

There is a known set of variables that are relevant to the study of MD and aggression and DV, such as sex (Archer, 2000; Bandura et al., 1996; Obermann, 2011a, 2011b), age (Capaldi, Knoble, Shortt & Kim, 2012; Offenhauer & Buchalter, 2011; Paciello et al., 2008; Author citation, 2015) and most importantly, social desirability (Saunders, 1991; Shorey, Cornelius & Bell, 2008). In the current study, we established two main objectives. First, we set out to analyze the relationships between the specific mechanisms of MD and the different manifestations of aggression (physical and verbal) and DV (physical and verbal-emotional), controlling the effect of sex, age, and social desirability. In this sense, we expected to find, on the one hand, a more significant relationship between MD and the physical manifestations of aggression and DV, and on the other hand, a predominance of the mechanisms of depersonalization over those of responsibility and rationalization. Secondly, we wanted to analyse the predictive power of MD mechanisms for the different types of aggression and DV, in order to identify those mechanisms that better predict each aggressive and violent manifestation. In terms of this second objective, we expected to find that MD will better predict the physical manifestations of aggression and DV, and that the predictive value of depersonalization will be stronger for these physical manifestations than for verbal or emotional manifestations.

Method

Participants

The study was performed on a sample of 424 individuals (38.9% males and 61.1% females) aged 15 to 25 years ($M = 18.80$; $SD = 2.69$): 54.7% between 15-18 years old, and 45.3% between 19-25 years old. All participants were White volunteers students (they were not given any form of compensation) from various educational centres in Spain: 42.9% college students and 57.1% middle school students. The entire sample had a partner or had partner/s during the year preceding the data collection. Regarding the type of relationship: 96.7% had a heterosexual relationship; 2.1% a homosexual relationship; and 1.2% a bisexual relationship. The length of the last dating relationship in the study sample was: less than a month (15.1%); between one and six months (17.7%); between six months and one year (18.6%); and over a year (48.6%). Finally, only 8.3% of participants cohabited with their partner.

Measures

Socio-demographic and dating relationships data. An *ad hoc* questionnaire was generated to collect data on sex, age, nationality, ongoing educational studies, length of the last relationship, type of relationship, and cohabitation.

Moral Disengagement. The Mechanisms of Moral Disengagement Scale (MMDS; Bandura et al., 1996; Spanish version, Author citation, 2017) evaluates the different mechanisms of MD. The Spanish version consists of 32 items that are assessed through a five-point Likert scale: from 1 = totally disagree to 5 = totally agree). The scale enables us to obtain a general composite MD score and eight partial scores, one for each MD mechanism (moral justification, euphemistic labelling, advantageous comparison, displacement of responsibility, diffusion or responsibility, distortion of consequences, dehumanization, and attribution of blame) and three higher order dimensions: (1) *disengagement by depersonalization*, consisting in

dehumanization and blaming of the victim (e.g., "some people deserve to be treated like animals"); (2) *disengagement by irresponsibility*, which minimizes the damage done, and displaces or diffuses responsibility for the aggression (e.g., "if a group decides together to do something harmful it is unfair to blame any one kid in the group for it"); and (3) *disengagement by rationalization*, that entails moral justification for the aggression, euphemistic labelling of the actions committed and the distortion of their harmful consequences (e.g., "it is alright to fight to protect your friends"). For the aim of this study, these three higher order scales have been used as representative dimensions of the set of MD mechanisms. For the study sample here, the following *Cronbach alpha* coefficients were obtained: *moral disengagement* (.89); *disengagement by depersonalization* (.75); *disengagement by irresponsibility* (.74); and *disengagement by rationalization* (.81).

Aggression. The Aggression Questionnaire (AQ; Buss & Perry, 1992; Spanish version, Andreu, Peña, & Graña, 2002) was used to assess aggressive behaviour in adolescents and young adults through two measures of aggression (physical and verbal) and two aggression-related emotions (anger and hostility). The questionnaire consists of 29 items evaluated using a five-point Likert scale: from 1 = completely false for me, to 5 = completely true for me). This instrument has a high global internal consistency, both the original version ($\alpha = .89$) and the Spanish version ($\alpha = .88$), and a confirmatory factorial analysis of the Spanish version confirmed the aforementioned tetradimensional structure (Andreu et al., 2002). For the present study, only the physical and verbal aggression scales were used. The general reliability of the instrument for the sample under analysis was estimated to be .89 using *Cronbach's alpha* coefficient, and the two subscales used in this study obtained estimates of .87 and .72 for physical and verbal aggression, respectively.

Dating violence. The Conflict in Adolescent Dating Relationships Inventory (CADRI; Wolfe et al., 2001; Spanish version; Fernández-Fuertes, Fuertes, & Pulido, 2006) is specifically

designed to detect the existence of violence in youth dating relationships and it consists of two subscales of 25 items each, known as the committed violence and suffered violence scales, as well as having another 20 items that function as distracters (e.g., "1a. I defended my point of view in the discussion). It is assessed by means of a four-point Likert scale: 0 = never; 1 = rarely; 2 = sometimes; 3 = frequently. Each scale (committed violence or suffered violence) is divided into five subscales of bidirectional forms of violence: physical abuse, verbal-emotional abuse, sexual abuse, relational abuse, and threatening behaviour. The reliability of the validation study in the Spanish population (Fernández-Fuertes et al., 2006), estimated using *Cronbach's alpha* coefficient, was good for both scales (committed violence, $\alpha = .85$; suffered violence, $\alpha = .86$). In this study, only the committed violence scale was used with a global internal consistency of .85 and an estimated $\alpha = .78$ for the verbal-emotional abuse and $\alpha = .67$ for the physical abuse subscales of committed violence.

Social Desirability. The Social Desirability Scale (SDS; Crowne & Marlowe, 1960; Spanish version; Ferrando & Chico, 2000) was designed to detect the tendency to voluntarily distort the image of oneself by the need to "dissimulate" or "make a good impression", and today, it is the most commonly used and popular tool to assess social desirability (Ferrando & Chico, 2000). The instrument consists of 33 items with a true/false response format (1 = true; 0 = false), some of which must be reverse-scored (e.g., "sometimes I have doubts about my ability to succeed in life"). The reliability of this scale, estimated using *Cronbach's alpha* coefficient, has been shown to be good in various studies, ranging from .73 (Strahan & Gervasi, 1972) to .82 (Reynolds, 1982). The Spanish version (Ferrando and Chico, 2000) also showed acceptable reliability ($\alpha = .78$). The global internal consistency for the sample under study was .76.

Procedure

The assessment was carried out on groups of 25-30 students from different education centres that agreed to participate in the study, and it was performed by three researchers experienced

in studies of aggression and violence. Prior to the evaluation, the participants were given an explanation on the overall aim of the study and some general instructions to complete the test booklets. The time required to complete the evaluation protocols varied between 45 and 60 minutes.

The study met recommendations and requirements of Bioethics Committee of *Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia* and the Ethical Principles of the American Psychological Association. Participation was voluntary, and the anonymity and confidentiality of the data was guaranteed throughout the procedure. All the participants provided their informed consent prior to entering the study, and in the case of minors, this was given by their parents, guardians or legal representatives.

Data Analysis

Pearson and point biserial correlation coefficients were examined to assess the association between all the study variables. Different hierarchical multiple linear regression analyses were carried out to examine the association between the mechanisms of MD (*depersonalization, irresponsibility* and *rationalization*) and AQ-aggression (total score, physical and verbal aggression), and the association between mechanisms of MD and CADRI-dating violence (total score, physical and verbal-emotional abuse). In step 1, potentially important variables were included in order to control for their possible influence, such as sex, age, and social desirability. Step 2 involved the analysis of the three mechanisms of MD. All analyses were performed using the SPSS 19.0 software.

Results

Relationships between moral disengagement, aggression, and dating violence

The total AQ score and that of the physical and verbal aggression subscales were directly and significantly related to the three mechanisms of MD (*depersonalization, irresponsibility*

and rationalization). Moreover, although the total CADRI score (committed violence) was directly related to the three mechanisms of MD, this relationship was of a lower magnitude than that of the relationships that were found between these mechanisms and the dimensions of AQ. In addition, the physical and verbal-emotional abuse dimensions of CADRI were only significantly associated with the mechanism of *disengagement by irresponsibility*.

Statistically significant correlations were found between AQ and CADRI, of medium effect size for the total scores of both instruments ($r^2 = .10$) and of a small magnitude for the correlations between the subscales related to behaviours of the same type ($r^2 = .02$): physical aggression in the AQ with physical abuse of CADRI; and verbal aggression in the AQ with verbal-emotional abuse of CADRI.

Moreover, social desirability was inversely correlated with all dimensions of the AQ and CADRI, and with the three mechanisms of MD. Similarly, age was inversely correlated with the dimensions of the AQ and with the three mechanisms of MD, but it was not significantly related to the dimensions of CADRI under study. Likewise, the variable of sex was related to the other variables. Specifically men scored higher than women in terms of the total AQ score, physical and verbal aggression, and the three MD mechanisms, particularly in rationalization ($r^2 = .14$; medium effect size). By contrast, women scored higher than men for the dimensions of CADRI, although with a small magnitude, as well as on the social desirability scale. A correlation matrix for the all study variables is presented in Table 1.

[Insert Table 1 here]

Predictive power of moral disengagement on aggression and dating violence

Different hierarchical multiple regression analyses were performed to study the predictive power of the three mechanisms of MD on the dimensions of the AQ (total score, physical aggression and verbal aggression) and CADRI (total score, physical abuse and verbal-

emotional abuse). The variables sex, age and social desirability were included as control variables in the first step and the three mechanisms of MD in the second step. The models were statistically significant in all dimensions with regards the AQ scores for aggressive behaviour (see Table 2): total score, $F(6, 417) = 60.03, p = .000$, physical aggression, $F(6, 417) = 48.94, p = .000$, and verbal aggression, $F(6, 417) = 23.39, p = .000$. Specifically, the *rationalization* mechanism was a significant predictor of the three dimensions of the AQ, while the *depersonalization* mechanism significantly predicted the total score of the AQ and the scores on the physical aggression dimension. By contrast, the *irresponsibility* mechanism only predicted the total AQ score. The mechanisms of moral disengagement managed to explain 11% of the variance in the total AQ score, 11% of the variance in the physical aggression dimension and 5% of the variance in the verbal aggression dimensions. Furthermore, the predictive power of the variables sex, age and primarily social desirability, on the dimensions of the AQ is noteworthy. Specifically, being male, of a younger age, and having a lower score in terms of social desirability had a predictive capacity of 35% on the total AQ score, of 29% on the physical aggression dimension and of 19% on verbal aggression dimension.

[Insert Table 2 here]

With respect to the DV scores obtained with the CADRI, the three multiple regression models were statistically significant to predict both the total CADRI score (committed violence, $F(6, 417) = 14.55, p = .000$) and the score of the CADRI dimensions: physical abuse, $F(6, 417) = 7.26, p = .000$; and verbal-emotional abuse, $F(6, 417) = 14.74, p = .000$. As shown in Table 3, the irresponsibility mechanism of MD was the only significant predictor of both total score and that of the verbal-emotional abuse dimension. No MD mechanism significantly predicted the physical abuse dimension (see Table 3). Moreover, sex and social desirability were variables that significantly predicted the CADRI dimensions. Specifically, being a woman and having a

lower score in terms of social desirability had a predictive capacity of 14% for the total CADRI score (committed violence subscales), of 7% for the physical abuse dimension and of 14% for the verbal-emotional abuse dimension.

[Insert Table 3 here]

Discussion

This work aimed to address two main objectives: firstly, to study the relationships between MD and aggression and DV in adolescents and young adults; and secondly, to analyze the predictive value of MD on the different types of aggressive and violent manifestations under study. In terms of the first objective, the most notable results reveal a significant association between the mechanisms of MD (*disengagement by depersonalization, disengagement by irresponsibility* and *disengagement by rationalization*) and the different manifestations of aggression and DV. As expected, the physical manifestations of aggression showed a stronger association than verbal manifestations of aggression, although this was only confirmed for aggression and not for DV. Moreover, the depersonalization mechanism of MD was not found to have prevalence over the other two mechanisms of MD (*disengagement by irresponsibility* and *disengagement by rationalization*), displaying a similar magnitude of significant associations. However, relationships between mechanisms of MD and DV were of less magnitude than MD-aggression and less intense than those found in a previous exploratory study (Author citation, in press). These results may suggest that DV is more independent or less closely related to socio-moral control mechanisms than general aggression, that is, there could be different control mechanisms for the different manifestations of aggressive behaviour. Given its cognitive-social nature, MD is likely to be more strongly related to instrumental aggression or that committed calmly, thus requiring some cognitive processing. In this sense, instrumental aggression (*proactive aggression*) is conceived as a “cold” and calculated behaviour, that is to

say, a premeditated means of obtaining some other goal; in contrast, hostile aggression (*reactive aggression*) is “hot” and impulsive, has an unplanned character and is motivated by a desire to harm someone (Anderson & Bushman, 2002; DeWall, Anderson, & Bushman, 2012). In any case, it would be interesting to investigate the relationships between MD and DV by introducing some measure of hostile and instrumental aggression to analyse empirically the aggressor’s motivation (Raine et al., 2006).

However, the significant associations between aggression and MD mechanisms found in this study are consistent with previous studies that consistently associated MD mechanisms with disinhibition of aggression and antisocial behaviour in adolescents and young adults (Bandura et al., 1996; Hyde et al., 2010; Paciello et al., 2008; Pelton, Gound, Forehand, & Brody, 2004), as well as with new forms of aggression like *cyber-aggression* (Pornari & Wood, 2010). Along these lines, it has been shown that MD is closely related to violent behaviour in adolescence, such as *bullying* (Hymel et al, 2005; Obermann, 2011a, 2011b), which includes different types of verbal, physical and relational aggression. Studies in adolescents have revealed that the individuals involved in episodes of abuse and harassment between peers, both perpetrators and witnesses of these behaviours, exhibit high levels of MD, and higher MD scores have been found in victims of *bullying* than in adolescents not involved in such dynamics of violence (Obermann, 2011a, 2011b). As indicated, adolescents who display more mechanisms of MD are more prone to have revenge-oriented ruminations, are more irritable, more inclined towards physical and verbal aggression, and they have a tendency to be involved more often in violent episodes (Obermann, 2011b).

With regards to the second objective pursued, concerning the predictive power of MD on the different manifestations of aggression and DV, the greatest proportion of the variance explained by the mechanisms of MD were for the two dimensions of the AQ: physical aggression and verbal aggression. By contrast, MD mechanisms had a much weaker predictive

power for the dimensions of CADRI, with hardly any difference between the predictive values of physical violence and those of verbal-emotional violence. Therefore, the initial hypothesis regarding the stronger predictive power of MD on physical versus verbal manifestations was only met by physical aggression in the AQ but not for physical DV in the CADRI. As suggested previously, this poor predictive value of MD on the DV could also be explained, at least in adolescents, by the independence of the socio-moral control mechanisms relevant to this particular type of violence.

Concerning the mechanisms of MD that best predicted each of the manifestations of aggression and DV, *depersonalization* (dehumanization of the victim and the attribution of blame) and *rationalization* (moral justification of aggression and minimization/distortion of its consequences) were the best predictors of physical aggression, whereas *irresponsibility* (advantageous comparison, displacement, diffusion of responsibility) exclusively predicted verbal-emotional DV. However, the mechanisms of MD did not predict physical DV. Nevertheless, when considering aggression as a single global dimension, *rationalization* is the best predictive mechanism, that is, aggression is justified and the harmful consequences are minimized or distorted (Bandura, 1990, 2002; Bandura et al., 1996).

As expected, *depersonalization* had a stronger significant contribution to physical but not verbal aggression. However, this was not the case for DV, for which *depersonalization* was not significantly related to either its physical or verbal manifestations, whereas the mechanism of *irresponsibility* was a significant predictor of verbal-emotional violence. The greater weight of *depersonalization* mechanisms on physical aggression may be due to the very seriousness of the physically aggressive manifestations, since they require a greater degree of dehumanization and less empathy than verbally aggressive manifestations. With regard to DV, it is possible that the emotional bond established between the partners plays a protective role against dehumanization. In this sense, future studies should examine the extent to which the emotional

bond and empathy with the partner determine the relationship between the mechanisms of *depersonalization* of victims and violent behaviour. The link between physical aggression and two of the three mechanisms of moral disengagement reveals the seriousness of such aggressive manifestations. Thus, inflicting physical aggression requires not only more or more intense MD but also, a combination of different mechanisms (*disengagement by depersonalization* and *disengagement by rationalization*) that act synergistically to aggravate violent manifestations. The close relationship between MD and aggressive behaviour is consistent with a recent meta-analysis on a global sample of 17,776 individuals in the 8-18 age range (Gini, Pozzoly & Hymel, 2014). This study showed a greater size effect on adolescents than on children, which might indicate that the use of these mechanisms requires a social background and a cognitive-moral development characteristic of older youths.

Within the few research studies carried out to date on the relationship between moral reasoning and DV, the results of the present work are in line with a study showing that men who displace responsibility for the damage inflicted on others are more likely to use physical aggression in their dating relationships (Feiring et al., 2002). Nevertheless, further research in this area will be needed to determine why MD mechanisms have less predictive power on DV than on other forms of violence (i.e.: aggression in general, bullying, cyber-bullying).

Finally, although the variables of *sex*, *age* and *social desirability* were not the subject of this study, they were included as covariates, indicating their relevance in the prediction of violent behaviour. Specifically, certain characteristics, such as being younger, male or having a lower social desirability, facilitate violent behaviour. These results are consistent with the literature regarding the influence of sex (Anderson & Bushman, 2002. Andreu et al., 2002), age (Brame et al., 2001; Gerbino, Caprara & Caprara, 2006) and social desirability (Saunders, 1991; Shorey et al., 2008) on violent behaviour. Specifically, social desirability contributes to the distortion

of the self-image, and to provide responses considered as socially acceptable or expected, therefore potentially masking the true responses.

Research limitations

This work has some limitations, mainly related to the cross-sectional nature of the data and the self-reported assessment of the variables under study. Although the social desirability of informants was evaluated and controlled, it would be advisable to compare the scores obtained in the scales studied here with those obtained from the external informants. It will be interesting in future research studies to explore the potential moderating role of sex, age and social desirability on mechanisms of MD and violent behaviours. Furthermore, the predictive value of MD should be analysed with longitudinal data where predictive variables temporarily precede the criteria variables. Due to the weak association between DV and the MD mechanisms explored, further studies will be needed to explain the reasons for these differences. The analysis of other variables, such as empathy, the motivations of aggressors (especially whether or not aggressive behaviour has instrumental value), and the severity of aggressive behaviours, could provide insight into the basis of these differences.

Research implications

The results of the present work show relationships of different intensity between mechanisms of MD, aggression and DV. On the one hand, it is particularly noteworthy the closely relationship of mechanisms of moral disengagement by *rationalization* (i.e. legitimization moral of violence and minimization/distortion of harmful consequences in others) with physical and verbal aggression and the important role of this mechanism in the prediction of aggression in general. In addition, moral disengagement by *depersonalization* (i.e. dehumanization and attribution of blame to victims) has a significant value in the prediction of physical violence.

On the other hand, the relationships between MD and aggression in courtship were less consistent, and only the moral disengagement by *irresponsibility* (i.e. displacement/diffusion of one's responsibility in aggressive behaviour) was a significant predictor of verbal-emotional abuse. Surprisingly, these results differ from a previous exploratory research (Author citation, in press) and future research is needed to confirm these findings.

Clinical and policy implications

This study has some clinical and policy implications, especially the results show the relevance of certain socio-cognitive and moral processes on attitudes and violent behaviour in adolescence, when processes of identity formation and the subsequent internalization of norms and values are of particular importance. Firstly, the relationships found between MD and aggression are in line of previous studies (Obermann, 2011a, 2011b; Paciello et al., 2008; Pelton et al., 2004) and suggest taking in account MD for the prevention of violence in adolescents, both aggression in general and dating violence. For this reason, knowing by children and adolescents of the concept of moral disengagement can make them think about the use of these socio-moral distortions in their own daily practice (Obermann, 2011a). Secondly, identification and discussion of specific mechanisms of MD associated with the different types of aggressive behaviour would be very useful as part of primary prevention of violence programmes in educational settings (Cornelius & Resseguie, 2007; Leen et al., 2013). Afterwards, the modification of biases and cognitive distortions inherent to the MD mechanisms in secondary prevention programmes with aggressors or potentially aggressive adolescents would be introduced in order to prevention of antisocial behaviour, bullying, cyber-bullying and DV at school. Finally, the results suggest that it is particularly important controlling social desirability in research on interpersonal violence and MD (Saunders, 1991; Shorey et al., 2008) in order to reduce the need to “look good” that usually occurs in this type of studies.

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Table 1

Descriptive and Pearson correlations for the variables included in the regression analysis

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. AQ total score	—										
2. Physical Aggression	.80**	—									
3. Verbal Aggression	.74**	.49**	—								
4. CADRI Total Score ^a	.31**	.23**	.15**	—							
5. Physical Abuse	.13**	.14**	.03	.64**	—						
6. Verbal-emotional Abuse	.29**	.17**	.15**	.93**	.47**	—					
7. Depersonalization ^b	.44**	.49**	.30**	.12*	.07	.07	—				
8. Irresponsibility ^b	.42**	.36**	.31**	.18**	.12*	.15**	.52**	—			
9. Rationalization ^b	.54**	.55**	.42**	.13**	.08	.09	.64**	.56**	—		
10. Age	-.33**	-.29**	-.26**	.06	.08	.03	-.24**	-.28**	-.40**	—	
11. Social Desirability	-.52**	-.39**	-.37**	-.32**	-.20**	-.28**	-.25**	-.23**	-.32**	.13**	—
12. Sex ^c	-.20**	-.35**	-.16**	.16**	.15**	.23**	-.24**	-.14**	-.38**	.15**	.10*
<i>M</i>	73.91	18.40	13.67	9.81	0.39	7.60	14.54	24.64	25.24	18.88	15.76
<i>SD</i>	16.98	7.42	3.74	7.16	1.07	5.04	5.45	7.07	7.26	2.70	4.96

Note. AQ = Aggression Questionnaire; CADRI = Conflict in Adolescent Dating Relationships Inventory; ^a = Abuse subscale; ^b = Mechanisms of Moral Disengagement Scale-Spanish version; ^c = point biserial correlation was calculated (values: '1' Males, '2' Females).

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

Table 2

Multiple Regression Analysis of Sex, Age, Social Desirability and Moral Disengagement (Depersonalization, Irresponsibility and Rationalization of the MMDS-S) in the AQ (Total Score, Physical and Verbal Aggression)

	AQ Total Score				Physical Aggression				Verbal Aggression			
	Const.	β	R^2_a	ΔR^2	Const.	β	R^2_a	ΔR^2	Const.	β	R^2_a	ΔR^2
Step 1	135.62		.35		44.03		.29		24.21		.19	
Sex		-.11**				-.29**				-.10*		
Age		-.25**				-.20**				-.20**		
Social Desirability		-.48**				-.34**				-.33**		
Step 2	36.85		.46	.11**	8.91		.40	.11**	6.70		.24	.05**
Depersonalization ^a		.11*				.22**				.02		
Irresponsibility ^a		.12**				.04				.07		
Rationalization ^a		.23**				.20**				.23**		

Note. MMDS-S = Mechanisms of Moral Disengagement Scale-Spanish version; ^a = Subscales of the MMDS-S; AQ = Aggression Questionnaire. Sex = '1' Boys, '2' Girls.
* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

Table 3

Multiple Regression Analysis of Sex, Age, Social Desirability and Moral Disengagement (Depersonalization, Irresponsibility and Rationalization of the MMDS-S) in the CADRI (Total Score, Physical and Verbal-emotional Abuse)

	CADRI Total Score				Physical Abuse				Verbal-emotional Abuse			
	Const.	β	R^2_a	ΔR^2	Const.	β	R^2_a	ΔR^2	Const.	β	R^2_a	ΔR^2
Step 1	2.87		.14		-.05		.07		7.32		.14	
Sex		.20**				.16**				.25**		
Age		.06				.08				.03		
Social Desirability		-.33**				-.22**				-.31**		
Step 2	-1.16		.16	.02**	-2.95		.09	.02*	-9.79		.16	.02**
Depersonalization ^a		-.02				.00				-.05		
Irresponsibility ^a		.14*				.08				.14*		
Rationalization ^a		.10				.10				.11		

Note. MMDS-S = Mechanisms of Moral Disengagement Scale-Spanish version; ^a = Subscales of the MMDS-S; CADRI = Conflict in Adolescent Dating Relationships Inventory. Sex = '1' Boys, '2' Girls.
* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$